

SALES FORCE MOTIVATION AND PERSONNEL PERFORMANCE OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANK IN PORT HARCOURT

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ABSTRACT:

Sales force motivation describes a sales force intrinsic enthusiasm and drives to accomplishment. Every sales force is motivated by something in his or her life. Motivating a sales force to work is the combination of fulfilling the sales force need and expectations from work and work place factor. That enables sales force motivation. Too many work places still act as if the sales force should be grateful to have a job. Managers are on power trip and sales force policies and procedure are formulated based on the assumption that you cannot trust sales force to do the right thing. In the banking sector, task and target are placed on sales for to delivery but the required motivation and benefits are delayed and even denied. Effective remuneration and recognition are sources of motivation to enhance these personnel to performance satisfactorily. Interview and questionnaires are administered to sales force in Port Harcourt. Their response has helped in analyzing the result in a simple percent format. It was found that motivation serves as a factor which influence performance and enhance personal performance. This study recommended that human capital management (HCM) in the commercial bank should develop policies that encourage employee to advance their careers. Employee should be engaged on a permanent terms in order to maximize high turnaround in performance. In addition, human capital managers should review compensation, incentive and salaries policies and pay sale force overtime worked.

KEYWORDS:

Sales Force Motivation. Rewards. Effective remuneration and Recognition. Personal Performance.

INTRODUCTION

In sales job, sales force has to deal with a lot of pressure because making the sale is not an easy task(Karki, 2011). Sales force feel detached from their organization as mostly they are engaged in off office duties and disconnected from any kind of support from their peers.Sales personnel need more motivation as compared to other jobs and compensation is a prime factor for their motivation. Designing motivation plans for sales force is important for motivating employees performance and enduring long term profitability of the banking sector.

Certain sector such as insurance, banking and business to business are considered to rely heavily on personal selling skill which requires efforts of individual sales people.Without effective motivation strategies, achieving organizational performance may be a challenging task to both small and large organization (Fatima 2017), Contend that organizational performance is a function of sales force motivation (Gitahi, 2014) opinion that incentives given to employees of the sales force in organization should form the largest in budget. (Gunter, 2011) suggest that the type and amount of compensation given by the organization determine not only the quality of sales force who can be hired but also creates motivation among the sales force (Jeseren 2015) acknowledges that compensation on sales force motivation is determined by monetary rewards which are measured in terms of financial gains such as salary and wages recognition, promotion, training and delegation.Sales force motivation is defined as the degree to which individual employee of the marketing department are contesting to achieve their objective if stimulated by financial and non-financial reward.

Despite the fact that sales force motivation is viewed to have a direct influence on personnel performance in a services firm (bank), it is observed that majority of the banks in Port Harcourt is finding it difficult to sustain personnel performance.Competition, changes of consumer performance, changes of technology and influence of globalization and changes in government policies towards the banking sector have not made banks to rethink on their sales force motivation in order to improve the personal performance.

High rate of unemployment, and constant loss of job in the state, and huge taxes paid to sustain the operation has contributed to poor sales force motivation in the banking sector.The quest for banks to even sustain profitability, has led to an alternative strategy of short-

changing the sales force and reduce performance. Even though extensive studies have been conducted by researcher internationally and locally, still it is noted that there existed a relationship in evidence on the relationship between motivations and personnel performance thus the need for this studies.

Onyanjo (2017), studied motivational strategies and sales force performance in the Insurance industry in Kenya. The study, found out that there existed a significant positive correlation between motivational strategies and sales personnel performance. However, it was noted that the study was confined to the insurance sector but not the banking sector. This apparent gap calls for a study in the banking industry in Nigeria. This study is designed to bridge this gap.

Research objective

1. To establish the influence of sale force motivation on personnel performance.
2. To access the influence of sales force training and welfare on performance in the banking sector in Port Harcourt.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Is there a significant relationship and positive relationship between motivation and personnel performance?

Is increment in financial incentive in terms of salary commission, bonus related to better performance?

Literature review

This study is anchored on motivation-hygiene theory founded by Herzberg in (1969). It argues that employees are likely to work effectively if motivated by intrinsic and extrinsic factor. Hygiene factors are regarded to be those job factors which must be existent of the work place for the employee to be motivated at work (John. 2012). Non-existence of these factors in an organization can lead to classification even though they do not guarantee positive satisfaction.

Hygiene factor when adequate in an organization can make employee to be motivated to perform vice-versa. Hygiene factor are also called dissatisfiers or maintenance factors as they intervene to minimize level of employee dissatisfaction (Mathias & Jackson 2008). The

hygiene factor that can make employee perform may include reasonable pay and wages, flexibility of administrative policies, fringe benefit attached to employee position, conducive working environment, good interpersonal relations among worker and job security (Aminu, 2011).

FalolaOsibanjo and Ojo (2014) acknowledged, argued that hygiene factor only cannot be considered to be the only motivators but also other factor termed as satisfiers can enhance employee motivation to perform such as recognizing the effort of hard working employee by top level manager, employee capacity to have sense of achievement from the job ability of the employee to develop his or career in the system through promotions. Ability to perform delegated duties effectively and meaningfulness of the work. Employees in an organization are likely to behave positively towards organizational goals if they find their jobs to be interesting or exciting and vice versa.

Despite extensive application of motivation-hygiene theory in human resources management literature. It is observed that the theory has some limitations which make operationalization and contextualization of its constructs to be uncertain. Theory assumes the correlation between satisfaction and productivity. Further, it is observed that satisfaction is multidimensional facet which is influenced and determined by multiple aspects. This complex to be measured from context to context. Additionally, it is observed that despite adequacy of satisfiers in an organization to some extent, organization may fail to accomplish their goals in the long term period (Ghansan, 2011).

The level of excitement and satisfaction among workers is not correlated to productivity and vice versa. However, this theory was applicable in this study based on the premise that commercial banks in Port Harcourt was likely to perform effectively if they refocused on employee promotion, training and create an enabling environment that that promotes self-motivation among workers.

SALES FORCE MOTIVATION AND PERSONNEL PERFORMANCE

Employee motivation is one of the vital tools, that help to enhance effective personnel performance (Aina&Omoniyi, 2014) affirms that it is vital for every organization to expect extra efforts and invest much in employee motivation as a process that objectives in the most

economics may (Akinyi, 2015) describe motivation as a reason for acting or behaving in a particular way.

Sales force motivation is a drive to sell a product or service to customer to achieve effective performance (Shahazadi, 2016) found a significant positive effect between motivation and employee performance. Ndibe (2014) in Nigeria also identified that the performance of a bottling companies was positively influenced by employee motivation. It was concluded that personnel productivity influenced by employee perception to motivate and training delivery style.

Sales force self-motivation and organization performance, recognition of employee are viewed to influence organizational productivity if effectively managed. Even though individuals may give different personalities, promotion, conducive working environment, good management style and personal relations are aspect considered to influence organizational productivity. Despite extensive empirical studies conducted by (Hafiz, 2017), it was acknowledged that employee self-motivation is multifaceted construct which reflect the effort of desire of individual worker to work towards organizational goals with minimal resistance employee cooperative attitude to management and ability to embrace change is largely dependent on how intrinsic and extrinsic factor that can serve as the driving forces of positive behaviours among workers.

Employee turnover and absenteeism are aspect attributed to low self-esteem among workers. High level of employee commitment to work not only make organization to experience improved productivity but also enhances stake holders image. Delvecchio and Wayner (2011) asserted that employee self-motivation is considered to be most important factor of organizational performance. Intrinsic motivation among worker is viewed to be superior to extrinsic motivation. Employee can be paid good amount of money in form of wages and salaries but if there is no self-motivation, less will be achieved. (Kimiru 2012) on the other hand established that employee recognition, delegation, promotion, recommendations and employee involvement is key decision in all aspect that inspires workers to achieve organizational goal. Inability of workers to identify employee unique skills or talent and lack of recognition can result to deteriorating performance of organizations in terms of profits and volume of sales. Customer loyalty is directly equated to employee commitment (Anyanjo 2017) postulated that performance of insurance companies was positively influenced by

employee training in contrast. This study will seek to examine the effect of sales force promotion, sales force training and sale force self-motivation on performance of commercial bank in Port Harcourt.

From the many findings of empirical studies, it was evident that much has been done with regards to sales force motivation practices and performance of firms in the manufacturing/ service sectors. It can be concluded that conceptual, contextual and methodological research gaps to exist in this areas.

CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

Remuneration

This consist of the fixed and monthly salary that is due for the salesforce. To include commission, bonus and allwonces. Sujan (2020), opin that a good remuneration plan plays a crucial role in motivation and increment in the performance of a Salesforce. It increases the ability and impact of the Salesforce and in consideration of the emerging external environment. This remuneration should be one that is what living and working for. It must be based with the current economic standard. Thus a remuneration must not be delay or belated.

- The objective of a good remuneration plan that can motivate a salesforce. should achieve:
- Motivate a salesforce by linking achievement to monetary value.
- It must attract and hold successful sales people by providing a good standard of living for them.
- It must be a reflection of the outstanding programme and also provide regulatory of income.
- It must direct the sales force to specific company sale objective by paying higher commission on product line.
- It must motivate the Salesforce to give the best customer satisfaction which in turn create repeated consumer.

Staff Promotion

Staff promotion means the ascension of an employee to a higher ranks. It involve increased salary, position, responsibilities, status and fringe benefit. Vantage circle (2003), opined that this aspect of job drives employee (Salesforce) the most, the ultimate crave for dedication and loyalty towards an organization.

Some of the benefits for sales force promotion include the following;

Expectation: When this goal is achieved the Salesforce work very hard. And when this is not achieved, the organization losses the psychological grip of the sales person.

Need management: Promotion brings about new responsibility that initial creativity and productivity. This innovation bring about better performance and customer satisfaction.

Motivation and Productivity; This is the biggest tool for learning, achievement and

Salesforce retention: When an employee get a chance to grow they stick to the company.

Cost effective: Internal Salesforce promotion is less or reduce hiring cost for organization.

Career growth: When an Salesforce grows in careers path, he is bound to put in his or her best in the organization.

Job Satisfaction

This is a feeling or recognition and appreciation that drive a sales personnel to a higher level of performance on the job. It brings about a sense of autonomy and control over your assignment, duty or task. Job satisfactions are product of a good work. Remuneration reward system and favourable working condition.

The effect of job satisfaction reflect in customer satisfaction, productivity and personnel performance on this job. The attitude of an unsatisfied personnel reaches the customer patronage and bring about negative referral this affect sales or the service.

Quality Service; The ability to retain customer is by offering them high-quality and at a relatively low cost in line with the service specification. Before a service is delivered and term satisfactory, the sales force attitude, gesture and body language must reflect a professional perception. It is only a satisfied personnel who is well motivated that can portray these conduct in the discharge of their sales function. Highly motivated staff generally prefer to give high service quality and performed best in the job function. This will always lead to repeated business.

The key performance indices of a bank sale force

- Deposit mobilization
- Account opening
- Retail risk asset
- Forex (foreign exchange)
- Customer service
- Customer relationship
- Market storm
- Account activation and reactivation
- E-channel solution
- Agency banking service and point of sales (POS) terminal business

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design was adopted. The population of this study was 50 respondent selected from the marketing department (DSA) sales unit of the 17 branches of Polaris bank in Port Harcourt.

Convenient sampling procedure was adopted in a form of interview without discrimination.

The simple percentage method was adopted to analyze the respondent.

The follow interview questions were asked concerning their job and their performance.

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

- Would you like to do this job for long time?
- Does your employer motivate you enough to do more?
- Do you see yourself fulfill doing this job?
- Does your incentive and bonus come as at when due?
- Does the bank recognize your input to the job?
- Have you been promoted in the last five years of working in the bank?
- Do you go for training regularly?
- Does your salary come every month?
- Have your salary being raised since you were employed in the bank?

- If a new job offer comes will you stay with the bank or leave immediately?

DATA ANALYSIS

Question 1

Would you like to do this job for a long time?

45	No	90%
4	YES	8%
1	–	NIL

Question 2

Do you feel your employer motivates you enough to do more?

40	NO	80%
3	Yes	6%
7	–	14%

Question 3

Do you see yourself fulfilled doing this job?

42	NO	84%
5	Yes	10%
3	–	6%

Question 4

Does your incentive come to you as at when due?

40	YES	80%
7	NO	14%
3	–	6%

Question 5

Does the bank recognize your input to the job?

46	NO	92%
4	Yes	8%

Question 6

Have you been promoted in the last five years of working in the bank?

45	NO	90%
5	–	10%

Question 7

Do you go for training regularly?

48	NO	90%
2	–	4%

Question 8

Does your salary come to you as at when due?

49	YES	98%
1	–	2%

Question 9

Have your salary been raised since you were employed in the bank?

48	NO	96%
2	–	4%

Question 10

If a new job offer comes will you stay or leave the bank?

40	YES	80%
5	NO	10%
5	–	10%

Discussion of Findings

This study established that sales force motivation will affect personnel performance in the banking industry. Sales force motivation demand that sales force should be adequately incorporated to the bank’s budget on training.

If sales force is trained and motivated, they will choose the job as a career and advance it. This study shows that if the bank motivates their sales force, they will perform better than they are doing current and will add value to the bank.

This study shows that why there is poor service performance is because most sales force do not see themselves fulfilled by doing the job and they term to do it haphazardly. This study shows that the sales forces do have incentivesbut are not paid on time. But the incentive is very small and cannot satisfy their basic need to do the job. The study shows that the bank does not recognize those sale forces that perform their work excellently welland do not encourage them to do better.

This study shows that most of the sale forces are stagnated in their career. They have not been promoted for a long time. This has an adverse psychological effect on personnel performance.

The study shows that there has not been regularly training for the sale force. This has a negative effect on performance on the job. The study shows that the salaries of the sale force are paid regularly and on time. This salary only keep them going, it does not enable them to achieve their career goal or give them better life, because the salary have not been raised for a long time. The study shows that since the sales job does not have job security, most of the sale force are not stable on the job. They move to another organizationat the slightest increase in pay in another organization.

Recommendation

This study recommends that human capital management (HCM) in the commercial bank should develop policies that encourage employee to advance their careers. Employee should be engaged on a permanent terms in order to maximize high turnaround in performance.

The study also recommend that human capital manager (HCM) should review compensation, incentive and salaries policies and pay sale force overtime worked.

REFERENCES

- Aina, O. O., & Omoniyi, A. T. (2014). The Effect of Job Enrichment Schemes On Selected Construction Workers in Nigeria. *Organization, Technology & Management in Construction*, 6(1).
- Akanbi, P. A. (2011). Influence of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on employees' performance.
- Akinyi, O. P. (2015). Effect of motivation on employee performance of commercial banks in Kenya: A case study of Kenya Commercial Bank in Migori County. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 1 (3), 1-17
- Asl, I. M., Nazari, A., & Raadabadi, M. (2015). Examining the Relationship between Job Enrichment and Performance: A Case Study of Nurses. *Asian Social Science*, 11(18), 108.
- Adeleye, A.D., Adegbite, S.A. & Aderemi, H. O. (2014). Training and manpower development in public research and development organizations. *International Journal of Academic research in Management*, 3(3), 257-275.
- Aigbepue S. & Mammud V.E (2012). Training, development and organisational performance. *Trans campus journals*, 10 (3), 1-13
- Aminu H (2011). Assessment of the impact of employee training on organizational performance of Vitafoam Nigeria PLC, Research Project. Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
- Brown, D. R. & Harvey, D. (2006). An experiential approach to organization development. (7th Ed). New Jersey: Pearson Education. Practice. 8th Edition. Kogan page limited, London
- Byrne, D. (2017). Data analysis and interpretation. Project Planner. 10.4135/9781526408570.
- Collis, J. & Hussey, R. (2014). *Business Research: A Practical Guide for Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students*. 4th edition, Palgrave Macmillan
- Daft, R. L. (2010). *New era of management (9th Ed.)* South-Western College, Cengage Learning.
- Emeti, C.I. (2011). *Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Performance in Paint Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State*. PhD Thesis, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State University
- Fatima, Zoha. (2017). Impact of Compensation Plans on Salesforce Motivation. *Review of Professional Management- A Journal of New Delhi Institute of Management*. 15. 70.

- Falola H.O, Osibanjo A. O & Ojo S. I. (2014). Effectiveness of training and development on employees' performance and organisation competitiveness in the Nigerian banking. *Industry bulletin of the Transylvania university of braşov series v: economic sciences*, 7(56), 1-24
- Flippo E. (1997): *Principle of Personal Management*. McGraw Hill. New York.
- Fisher, C. M. (2010). *Researching and Writing a Dissertation: An Essential Guide For Business Students*. 3rd ed. Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall:808.066658 FIS & e-book.
- Gegenfurtner, A. (2013). Dimensions of motivation to transfer: A longitudinal analysis of their influence on retention, transfer, and attitude change. *Vocations and Learning*, 6(2), 187-205.
- Gitahi, S. N. (2014). *Effect of Workplace Environment on the Performance of Commercial Banks Employees in Nakuru Town*. PhD Thesis. Egerton University Guest, G. (2012). *Applied thematic analysis*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage. P. 11
- Gunter Walden, K. T. (2011). Apprenticeship Training in Germany still a future-oriented model for recruiting skilled workers? *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 305-322
- Hair, J.F., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., & Anderson, R.E. (2015). *Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective*, 7th Edition. Harlow: Pearson Education.
- Howard S. Q (2012) effect of employee training on the perceived organisational performance of. A print-media industry in Ghana *European journal of business and management* issn 2222-1905 (paper) ISSN 2222- 2839 (online) vol 4, no.15, 2012
- Jain, R., & Kaur, S. (2014). Impact of work environment on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 4(1), 1-8.
- Jeserem, I. (2015). *The perceived relationship between reward management practices and employee performance at the Kenya Post Office Savings Bank*. PhD Thesis. University of Nairobi
- Jilani, E. M., & Juma, M. D. (2013) *Contingent Rewards as a Strategy for Influencing Employee Engagement in Manufacturing Companies: Case Study of Williamson Tea Kenya Limited*.
- John, A. G., Francis, A. I., & Chukwu, I. I. (2012). Improving Sales Performance through Sales Force Motivation Strategies: A Study of Pharmaceutical Firms in Nigeria. *Int. J. Buss. Mgt. Eco. Res*, 3(5), 620-626.
- Kaplan, R. & Norton, D. (2010). Strategic focus organization performance management system to a strategic management system. *California Management Review*, 30-35.

- Kenya Association of Manufacturers Report (2018). Retrieved from <http://www.kam.co.ke>
- Kimiru, V. W. (2012). Motivation and satisfaction as functions of Perceptions of reward: a case study of employees of Kenya Revenue Authority. PhD Thesis. JKUAT
- Kun, F. D; Cowden R. & Karodia, A. M. (2014). Impact of training and development on employee performance: a case study of second consulting Singaporean Journal of business. economics, and management studies 3 (3)
- Malaolu, V. A. & Ogbuabor, J. E. (2013). Training and manpower development, employee productivity and organizational performance in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*, 2(5), 163-177.
- Mathis, R.L., & Jackson, J.H. (2008). *Human Resource Management*. (12th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Marumbwa, J., Makore, A. & Mudondo, C. D. (2013). The impact of compensation initiatives on sales forces performance: A case study of the insurance industry in the Southern region, Zimbabwe. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR)* 8(6), 71-79.
- Mertler, C.A. & Vannatta, R. A. (2010). "Advanced and Multivariate Statistical Methods, 4th Ed.". Los Angeles
- Milkovick, G.T. & Boudreau, J.W. (2004). *Personnel, human resource management: A diagnostic approach* (5th ed.). Delhi: Business Publications Inc.
- Mthokozisi, M. & Clifford, K. H. (2015). Training and development as a tool for improving basic service delivery; the case of a selected municipality, *Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Science*, 133-136
- Muchai, M.M. & Benson, M. A. (2013). Effect of Employee Rewards and Recognition on Job Performance in Kenya's Public Sector, A Case Study of Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company Ltd. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 4(10), 151-158.